

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D1.12 Second yearly documentation and minutes of project meetings

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I. Introduction

During the second year of the project, the project members continued to engage with each other through a number of different meetings. These took place via telephone, video conferencing, or face-to-face. In general, these meetings can be divided into two different categories: operational and governance/strategy.

Meeting category	Meeting type	Method(s)	Frequency
1. Operational	Work Packages	Phone, video conferencing, face-to-face	Variable depending on task at hand
	WGIS (Work Group on Identification and Standards)	Video conferencing, face-to-face	Weekly, bi-weekly, monthly, bi-monthly
2. Governance/strategy	Executive Committee	Video conferencing and face-to-face	Monthly
	Steering Committee	Video conferencing and face-to-face	Every three months
	General assembly and the Project Advisory Board **	Face-to-face	Yearly

** The second annual Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly meeting, which falls under the “Governance/strategy” category, was originally scheduled for 5-6 May 2020. This has been postponed until autumn 2020 due to the current extraordinary circumstances due to the Covid-19 pandemic. For further details, see [Project Advisory Board \(PAB\) and General Assembly](#).

Additionally, an informational meeting in Brussels for interested and potential external stakeholders was originally scheduled on 24 March 2020. This has also been postponed due to the situation caused by Covid-19. The Executive Committee and the Steering Committee, along with other auxiliary staff members, are working to concretise the plans.

This report documents the main content of the different types of meetings that have been realised during the second year. At the same time, this report will not reproduce the detailed minutes of each meeting, because the abundance of these precise details would not be interesting or insightful for this report’s audience. Instead, we chose to use this report as an opportunity to share the current meeting organisations, important decisions and contents, as well as reflections for better execution of future meetings.

II. Meeting contents/minutes

During the year, the main contents/decisions of the different types of meetings have been the following:

1. Operational meetings

Work Packages

These meetings are conducted within and across Work Packages and institutions to advance operational progress. As noted in the above table, the methods vary from phone/video conferencing/face-to-face meetings. Some Work Packages hold regular, periodical meetings for longer-term tasks, while other Work Packages organise their meetings on an as-needed basis. In order to facilitate project coherence, some Work Packages include the project manager in the meetings. Additionally, the work packages hold catchup meetings with the project manager as necessary.

In the second year of the project, according to the conclusions made at the first General Assembly in 2019, there was a consensus to encourage more inter-Work package and/or inter-institutional collaborations. In particular, this need was highlighted within Work packages 5-7 and 9, or the more “technical” Work packages of the project. In January 2020, a face-to-face meeting was held among these “technical” colleagues of the project, where each work package shared its progress so far. A discussion was then held on how to synchronise the work among these groups going forward and to potentially change the communication practices in place. It was agreed as a result of this meeting that the WGIS group will continue to play a crucial role in coordinating key issues on the common data model. Further, these “technical” work packages will increase knowledge sharing by sending around their deliverables to this group (which had previously been only sent to the Executive committee, and sometimes as well to the Steering committee).

The content and topics are too wide and varied to be described in this report, but in essence, the results of these meetings are the decisions made to drive the project forward according to the project proposal and the deliverables/milestones timelines. In other words, the results of these meetings can be seen in the project deliverables and milestones, as well as the content presented in the [Governance and strategy meetings](#) (see below).

WGIS (Work Group on Identification and Standards)

The WGIS group is comprised of the project members across the consortium institutions whose tasks include (meta)data identification and standardisation. The work packages involved are primarily 4, 5, 6, 7, and 9. The meetings take place every two weeks via video conferencing. One of these are monthly key decision-making meetings which also include the members of the Executive and Steering committees.

In 2019, the purpose of the group is to ensure coherence among the work packages, and for the project as a whole, on these topics. Participants have the opportunity to bring forth topics and progress to share, as well as to ask for feedback and discussion on issues that they are working on. From January 2020, WGIS has been incrementally discussing and deciding on EURHISFIRM’s data standards and the respective interfaces to the project’s process model.

2. Governance and strategy meetings

Executive Committee

The Executive Committee meets on a monthly basis (via video conferencing, with a face-to-face meeting every semester). The members consist of: Angelo Riva (École d'Économie de Paris), Jan Annaert (Universiteit Antwerpen), and Wolfgang König (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt). The meetings are also accompanied by the project manager (based at the École d'Économie de Paris) for purposes of alignment with the Executive Committee's decisions with the project and the work packages as a whole.

Key topics from previous meetings include:

- ▶ Project execution (from both scientific and administrative perspectives) and ensuring coherence among the different work package workflows
- ▶ Management of current and potential partnerships as well as the project's position in the overall research infrastructure community
- ▶ Overall governance and protocols, such as internal and external communications, as well as resource monitoring (human resources, finances, materials, etc.)
- ▶ Risk management.

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee meets every three months (via video conferencing, with a face-to-face meeting every semester). The participants consist of the work package leaders (the Executive Committee members are thus inherently members of the Steering Committee). The Steering Committee meetings are also attended by the project manager (to ensure alignment of the project strategy among the Executive Committee, the Steering Committee, and the Work Packages), as well as other relevant person(s) for the agenda at hand (for example, if a particular topic/concept will be discussed and will be presented by a project team member). The meeting topics are governance- and strategy-related, with a greater emphasis to the technical and content implementation of the project and the consortium coordination overall.

Key topics discussed in the past meetings include:

- ▶ Agreement on key design decisions and action points concerning the overall project direction
- ▶ Feedback on specific topics presented by work packages
- ▶ Partnerships and collaborations with other European infrastructures and the stakeholder community
- ▶ Organisation of key meetings (general assembly, informational meeting for external stakeholders).

Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly

The Project Advisory Board (PAB) meets yearly, in conjunction with the General Assembly. The PAB provides feedback on the project progress and advises on key strategic questions. These serve as crucial perspectives upon the project's overall direction and governance. The General Assembly is an extension of the PAB meeting, which summarises the issues discussed within the PAB and opens the discussion to

the external invited guests and interested stakeholders. This meeting also includes further detailed progress per work package and is an important opportunity for feedback and alignment from the entire consortium on these advancements.

The first annual Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly meeting was held at the Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (work package 2 lead beneficiary) on 15-16 March 2020. The outcomes from this meeting is documented on the project website: https://eurhisfirm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Eurhisfirm_SummaryofPABandGA_Final.pdf.

The second annual PAB and GA meeting was originally scheduled slightly after the first 24 months of the project, to take place on 5-6 May 2020 at the Queen's University of Belfast (work package 8 lead beneficiary) and organised together with the Wroclaw University of Economics and Business. However, due to the current Covid-19 pandemic, this meeting has been postponed until autumn 2020. The location remains unchanged. The new date, as well as possible new organisation topics, will be discussed at the next Steering Committee meeting in May 2020.

III. Conclusions: going forward and reflections on future organisation

During the second year, many fruitful meetings and collaborations have taken place for the project. Going forward, below are some reflections to increase the strengths of these collaborations:

- ▶ Last year, we have proposed to increase face-to-face meetings among work package members leading key topics. This has proved to be challenging to organize as frequently as we had hoped, due to the large number of people involved. Further, with the Covid-19 crisis, it will be necessary to depend even more upon remote-working. Therefore, we will continue to hold meetings regularly by video conferencing and to encourage this medium for communication, which are, in many cases, more effective than less direct modes of communication such as email.
- ▶ Good documentation of key decisions made during meetings remains crucial, in particular as the project topics become more involved and developed. With many people collaborating on different topics, it is essential that all people involved have the same understanding of the decisions made and on the goals going forward. To ensure this, the key meetings should have a designated meeting note taker, who then sends the document to the participants after the meeting for their approval.